

STUDY OF THE PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES, ANTIOXIDANT AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF HUMIC ACIDS OF COAL FROM KAZAKHSTAN DEPOSITS OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

**Kairbekov Zh.
Esenalieva M.Z.
Suimbaeva S.M.*
Dzheldybaeva I.M.
Kairbekov A.A.**

NPJSC Al-Farabi Kazakh National University,
Research Institute of New Chemical Technologies and Materials Almaty, Kazahstan.
e-mail: suimbayeva@gmail.com tel.: +7(727)2921786; +77012370003
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17343497>

Currently, Kazakhstan market of medicines is filled with quite expensive antioxidant drugs mainly of foreign production. The country needs domestic medicines and medicinal preparations that can compete with foreign analogues. In this regard, research on the development of innovative import-substituting drugs based on humic substances of peloids are of particular relevance and practical importance. One of the interesting and promising sources of biologically active substances (BAS) in terms of economic and therapeutic efficacy are peloids, in particular, coal, which is a complex of both inorganic and organic substances.

In this paper, the physicochemical, antioxidant and biological properties and elemental analysis of coals and their humic acids (HA) of the Oi-Karagai and Kiyakty deposits of the Republic of Kazakhstan were studied. The composition of the isolated HA was confirmed by IC method. According to the data obtained, it can be seen that the spectra of the coal deposits have both similarities and differences in the identified absorption bands. HA spectra are fully consistent with the literature data and a comparative analysis of the infrared spectra of HA from coals shows that they have a similar structure, the structural elements of which are similar functional groups of carbonyl, hydroxyl and aliphatic nature. The presence of paramagnetic centers (PMC) of coals and their HA was studied by the EPR method. From the obtained EPR spectra it follows that all HA preparations of peloids are characterized by the presence of paramagnetic centers with a g-factor value of higher than 2.00, which indicates the presence of free radicals in the peloid and HA molecules due to a highly delocalized electron cloud. The presence of "narrow" EPR signals indicates that humic substances are polymers with a well-developed system of conjugated bonds.

It has been established that the quantitative determination of the antioxidant properties of HS of coals can be carried out by the amperometric method by the value of the total content of antioxidants. The results of the amperometric determination of the antioxidant properties of the HA of the studied coals indicate that they have antioxidant activity, and this will allow to use it as a natural biologically active substance for drugs. The high antioxidant activity of HA makes it possible to recommend them for use in technical areas and in medicine as promising nanoscale antioxidants of natural origin and as a basis for the development of new classes of drugs.

Experimental data on the determination of the biological activity of humic acids by phytotesting demonstrated that one of the factors influencing biological activity is the concentration of the humic preparations used. The highest phytoactivity index for all tested samples of humic preparations occurs at concentration of 0.005%. It should be noted that HAs has a positive effect on seed germination energy, root length and sprout height.

MPHAPP

THE 6TH INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL
CONFERENCE "MODERN PHARMACEUTICS: ACTUAL
PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS"
TASHKENT, OCTOBER 17, 2025

in-academy.uz

The work was carried out with the financial support of the Committee of Science of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan within the framework of the project AP26194161 "Development of methods of directed chemical modification of lignite humic acids in order to increase antioxidant and biological activity and expand the areas of application".